

Metal Chelates of Biscyclohexanedionenaphthalenedihydrazone

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Reaction of aryldiazonium salts with 1,3-cyclohexanedione lead to 1,2,3-cyclohexanetrione-2-aryl-hydrazone¹. Such compounds have been extensively used as precursors of potential antidiabetic drugs². These hydrazones form stable chelates with several transition metal ions³. Our interest⁴ in the synthesis and characterisation of new polydentate and macrocyclic ligand systems through the reaction of aryldiazonium and tetrazonium salts with 1,3-diketones and metal 1,3-diketonates, led us to synthesise a new polydentate ligand by coupling tetrazotised 1,8-diaminonaphthalene with 1,3-cyclohexanedione to yield 2,2'-(1,8-naphthalenedihydrazone)bis(1,2,3-cyclohexanetrione), H₂L and its Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) of the reaction product of naphthalene-1,8-tetrazonium ion with 1,3-cyclohexanedione indicate that one equivalent of the tetrazonium salt coupled with two equivalents of cyclohexanedione.

Thus the ir spectrum of the ligand is characterised by the presence of two strong bands at 1 720 and 1 665 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively to the stretching of the free and hydrogen bonded carbonyl functions³⁻⁵ and a medium intensity band at 1 618 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The broad band at 2 400-3 350 cm⁻¹ indicates the hydrogen-bonded nature of the NH groups. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound shows a low field two-proton signal at 15.511 ppm, due to the strong intramolecularly hydrogen bonded -NH....O=C groups of the molecule³⁻⁵. The integrated intensities of all other protons agree well with the structure. That the C-3 and C-5 protons are in slightly different electronic environment is evident from the observed chemical shift data (Table 1) of the alicyclic protons. The FAB mass spectrum of the compound is dominated by an intense (P + 1)⁺ peak (*m/z* 405). The appearance of a peak at *m/z* 281 (P-

C₆H₆O₂N)⁺ indicates that cleavage occurs first at one of the N-N bonds, followed by the scission of the second N-N bond (fragment of *m/z* 155, which is the base peak in the spectrum). Such N-N bond scission is typical of aryl-hydrazones of 1,3-diketones^{4,6}.

The metal complexes : All the metal complexes (Table 1) behave as non-electrolytes (sp. cond. < 10 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in methanol) and do not contain the anion of the metal salt used for their preparation. The Cu^{II} complex shows normal magnetic moment (1.77 B.M.) and the Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

The free carbonyl band of the ligand remained almost unaffected on complexation. The hydrogen bonded carbonyl band of the ligand disappeared and instead a new band appeared at about 1 570 cm⁻¹ assignable to the stretching of metal bonded carbonyl functions⁶ in the spectra of all the complexes. The 3 400-2 400 cm⁻¹ ligand band cleared up in the spectra of all the complexes and weak bands appeared at about 2 850 and 2 930 cm⁻¹ (CH₂) and about 3 050 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C-H) in the spectra of the complexes. The two medium intensity bands at about 550 (M-N) and 425 cm⁻¹ (M-O)⁶ observed in the spectra of the complexes. In the ¹H nmr spectra of the Zn^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes (Table 1), the low field signal of the ligand due to the chelated hydrazone protons disappeared and the multiplet pattern of the alicyclic proton signals remained as such. This indicates the replacement of the hydrazone protons of the ligand by metal ion. The formulation of the complexes is strongly supported by the mass spectra of the complexes. Thus the presence of a P⁺/(P + 1)⁺ peak of appreciable intensity is characteristic of the spectra of all the complexes. Peaks due to M₂L and M₂L₂ are also observed. Similarly, peaks corresponding to the elimination of the cyclohexanedione moieties are also observed in the spectra. Formation of several metal containing fragments

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	M p (°C)/ (Colour)	Elemental Analysis % Found/(Calcd)					δ (Aryl)	δ (Methylene)		
		C	H	N	O	M				
H ₂ ncy	160 (Green)	64 73 (65 35)	4 20 4 95	13 24 13 86	15 65 15 84)	—	7 963-7 265 (6H, m)	2 778 (2H, t)	2 629 (2H, t)	2 154-2 068 (2H, m)
	248 (Black)	56 52 (56 71)	3 40 3 87	11 87 12 03	12 96 13 75	13 10 13 74)	—	—	—	—
Cu(ncy)	>300 (Brown)	56 76 (57 30)	3 42 3 91	11 66 12 16	13 24 13 89	11 65 12 74)	7 983-6 986 (6H, m)	2 885 (2H, t)	2 499 (2H, t)	2 269-2 018 (2H, m)
Ni(ncy)	>300 (Brown)	56 12 (56 49)	3 76 3 85	11 78 11 98	13 56 13 70	13 80 13 97)	7 979-7 012 (6H, m)	2 862 (2H, t)	2 501 (2H, t)	2 258-2 116 (2H, m)

can be located in the spectra of the chelates. Such peaks can be easily recognised based on the natural abundance of the various isotopes of metal ions.

Thus ir, ^1H nmr and mass spectral data strongly support the dibasic tetradentate nature of the ligand.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by coupling tetrazotised 1,8-diaminonaphthalene with 1,3-cyclohexanedione. 1,8-Diaminonaphthalene was tetrazotised using nitrosyl sulphuric acid as reported⁸. The tetrazonium salt solution (0.01 mol) was added with stirring into a methanolic solution of 1,3-cyclohexanedione (0.02 mol, 2.24 g in 10 ml ethanol). Sodium acetate was added to keep the pH of mixture around 7. The resulting green product washed with water and crystallised from hot methanol, yield 75%.

Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of a methnolic solution of the ligand (0.001 mol) with a methanolic solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.001 mol) for ~ 2 h on a boiling water-bath. The resulting complex was washed with water and methanol and dried

under reduced pressure, yields 45–60%.

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a PE 983 spectrophotometer, nmr on a Bruker 400 mH spectrometer and mass spectra on a JEOL/SX-102 spectrometer (FAB using argon and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol/glycerol as the matrix).

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